

Potentiometric Study of Cu(II) Complexes of 1 : 2-Dihydroxy Benzene 3 : 5-Disulfonic Acid

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The interaction of Cu^{++} ion with 1:2-dihydroxy benzene 3:5-disulfonic acid was investigated at 0.036M, 0.056M, 0.076M and 0.116M ionic strengths in aqueous medium by Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique at 30°. It was observed that Cu^{++} forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with this ligand around 4.5 and 7.0 p^H respectively. The ionic strength data were used : (i) to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes and (ii) to understand the mechanism of the complexation reaction.

A number of metal complexes of benzene and naphthalene sulfonic acids are reported¹. Recently Banerjee et al, have investigated spectrophotometrically, the Fe(III) complexes of 8-hydroxy-quinoline-7-sulfonic acid and 1 : 8-dihydroxynaphthalene 3 : 6-disulfonic acid². We have investigated transition metal complexes of some phenolic ligands³. The present study is a part of our work taken for understanding the nature of transition metal complexes of phenolic ligands.

Experimental :

Materials :

Copper was used in the form of its perchlorate and its concentration in aqueous solution was estimated by EDTA⁴. Perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate and sodium hydroxide used were of A.R. grade. The ligand, 1 : 2-dihydroxy-benzene-3 : 5-disulfonic acid (disodium salt) was obtained from Schuchardt (Germany).

pH Meter :

ELICO pH meter LI-10 was used for the measurement of pH values. The accuracy of this pH meter, was of ± 0.05 pH unit. The pH meter was standardised by buffer solution at pH 4.01 and pH 9.11 (30°).

Calvin-Bjerrum titration :

The experimental procedure involved the potentiometric titrations of carbonate free solution of (i) free $\text{HClO}_4(1.00 \times 10^{-2}M)$, (ii) free HClO_4

$(1.00 \times 10^{-2}M) + 1 : 2$ -dihydroxy-benzene-3 : 5 disulfonic acid $(1.514 \times 10^{-2}M)$, (iii) free $\text{HClO}_4(1.00 \times 10^{-2}M) + 1 : 2$ -dihydroxy-benzene-3 : 5-disulfonic acid $(1.514 \times 10^{-2}M) +$ copper perchlorate $(4.00 \times 10^{-4}M)$ and (iv) free $\text{HClO}_4(1.00 \times 10^{-2}M) +$ copper perchlorate $(4.00 \times 10^{-4}M)$ against sodium hydroxide $(0.11M)$, added from microburette.

The ionic strength of the solution for each set was maintained constant by the addition of appropriate amount of 1M solution of sodium perchlorate solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through an assembly containing the electrodes, to keep away CO_2 .

Results :

Proton-ligand stability constants :

The 1 : 2-dihydroxy-benzene-3 : 5-disulfonic acid was taken in the form of its disodium salt. The two $-\text{SO}_3\text{Na}$ groups must have dissociated in water to give Na^+ ions and the anionic ligand. This can

be represented as and will be designated as H_2L^- .

The acid + reagent curve was found to be coinciding with the acid curve upto pH 6.0. Later on it deviated from the acid curve and the deviation increased with increase of pH.

The \bar{n}_A (proton-ligand formation number) values were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁶. The minimum value of \bar{n}_A upto pH 10.0 was 1.06. This shows that only one -OH group is dissociated upto that pH. The pK_1 value was calculated by half-integral as well as by pointwise calculations. The accurate value of pK_2 , the dissociation constant of second -OH group could not be determined, because of the limited accuracy of glass electrode above pH 10.0. This value was however determined by noting down the pH at which $\bar{n}_A=1$ and using the expression: $2pH_{\bar{n}_A=1} = pK_1 + pK_2$.

The value obtained was 12.91 and should be considered to be rough. Kabadi et al.⁶ have adopted this method for the determination of pK_2 values of salicylic acid.

pK values of the two -OH groups are 7.86 and 12.91 at 0.116M ionic strength and should be ascribed to the -OH group in the 2nd and 1st position respectively. This is because of the metaorienting sulphonic groups at 3rd and 5th position will render carbon at second position positive, which will favour the overall mesomeric effects of the groups and therefore -OH at second position will dissociate first. Mesomeric effects of $-SO_3H$ and -OH from first position will oppose, resulting in comparatively poor dissociation of -OH group in that position.

Metal-ligand stability constant :

The possibility of complex formation between Cu^{2+} and the ligand anion was initially noted from the following points : (i) The pH of hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} ion obtained from the deviation of copper ion curve and from the acid curve is 5.5. The departure of $HClO_4$ + reagent + copper perchlorate curve from the $(HClO_4 + reagent)$ curve was observed around pH 4.25 in the media of different ionic strengths. This indicated that the complexation commences before the hydrolysis of copper ions sets in. The value of \bar{n} (metal ligand formation number) was calculated by using the Irving and Rossotti expression⁶. (ii) The solutions employed

being very dilute, the probability of existence of polynuclear species under experimental conditions is not expected to be high.

The maximum values of \bar{n} before the pH of precipitation was 1.9. This indicated the presence of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in solution

The values of $pL = -\log [L]$, where $[L]$ is the free ligand concentration, were calculated and plotted against \bar{n} to get the formation curve. Approximate values of $\log K_1$ and K_2 were obtained by half integral method and the accurate values by pointwise calculations. These values at various ionic strengths are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1— pK_1 VALUES OF 1 : 2 DIHYDROXY-BENZENE-3 : 5-DISULFONIC ACID AND $\log K_1$ AND $\log K_2$ VALUES OF ITS CU(II) COMPLEXES AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS.

μ	pK_1	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
0.036	8.10	6.27	3.90
0.056	8.08	6.20	4.05
0.076	7.94	6.13	4.14
0.116	7.86	6.03	4.32

Discussion

The potentiometric values of stability constants at different ionic strengths could be utilized to know the exact mechanism by which the complexation occurs at different pH values. The analysis of the data was initially done by the Brønsted equation 1.

$$\log k = \log K^0 + A \Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where A is the Debye-Huckel constant, ΔZ^2 is the difference in the square of the charges of the product and reactant ions and K^0 is the formation constant at zero ionic strength.

The value of A used was 0.57617. The plots of pK_1 , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ (Fig. 1) gave the following results :

(i) All the four points fall on a straight line in all the plots.

(ii) The magnitude of ΔZ^2 observed for each plot along with the expected ones, for different probable reactions are presented below :

No.	Reaction equilibrium	Constant	Slope value $s/A = \Delta Z^2$	
			Expected	Observed
1.	$H_2L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons HL^{2-} + H^+$	pK_1	+6.0	+3.0
2.	$Cu^{2+} + H_2L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuHL^- + H^+$	$\log K_1$	-6.0	-2.4
3.	$CuHL^- + H_2L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons Cu(HL)^{2-} + H^+$	$\log K_2$	12	7.0

The slope values observed in all the cases are less than the expected, and do not therefore give a conclusive evidence regarding magnitude of the charge of the reacting species. The discrepancy may be due to the limited applicability of the Brönsted equation. The use of the equation 2, which is an approximation of equation 3 and is obtained by taking βa_i equal to unity (assuming $a_i = 3.04 \text{ \AA}$ for all electrolytes) was made to determine the slope values. The latter equation is obtained using modified Debye-Huckel equation

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A \Delta Z^2 \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (2)$$

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A \Delta Z^2 \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \beta a_i \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2a, 2b and 2c show the linear plots of pK_1 , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$ with the slope value +4.3, -3.7 and 4.3 respectively. It seems, there-

fore, that the modified Debye-Huckel equation also does not show much improvement in the slope values.

The discrepancy between the expected and the observed slope values was thought to be due to the fact that concentration and not activity terms were used in the calculations of stability constants. The expressions for K and K^0 were rectified with the help of modified Davies equation⁸.

$$-\log f_i = A Z_i^2 \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

which gave the relation between K and K^0 as

$$\log K = \log K^0 + 0.5161 \Delta Z^2 \times \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\} \text{Log}$$

K values were plotted (Figs. 3a and 3b) against

$\left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\}$ and the magnitude of ΔZ^2 was

estimated. All the four points corresponding to

Fig. 1 (a)

Fig. 1 (b)

Fig. 1 (c)

Fig. 2 (a)

Fig. 2 (b)

Fig. 2 (c)

Fig. 3 (a)

Fig. 3 (b)

Fig. 3 (c)

0.015M, 0.056M, 0.076M and 0.116M ionic strengths fall on a straight line in both the plots. The observed slope values are -6.3, 12.6 and +5.8 for $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and pK_1 plots respectively.

The agreement between the expected and the observed slope seems to be fairly good and the reactions 2 and 3 seem to be following the mechanism given earlier. This confirms that one of the -OH group of the ligand, remains intact during complexation. For if both the -OH groups were involved the 1 : 1 complexation would have occurred by the reaction $Cu^{2+} + H_2L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons CuL^{2-} + 2H^+$ and the magnitude of ΔZ^0 would have been -2.0. The thermodynamic values of stability constants observed from various plots are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS (pK_1^0 , $\log K_1^0$ AND $\log K_2^0$)

Plot	pK_1^0	$\log K_1^0$	$\log K_2^0$
(Fig. 1)	8.44	6.56	3.24
(Fig. 2)	8.43	6.60	3.20
(Fig 3)	8.62	6.72	2.90

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References :

1. A. E. Martell, 'Stability Constants'. Special Publication No. 17, The Chemical Society, London, 1964.
2. S. K. Banerjee and K. C. Shrivastava, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 686.
3. D. V. Jahagirdar and D. D. Khanolkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1105.
4. G. Schwarzenbach, 'Complexometric titrations', Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, p. 69.
5. H. Irving and H. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. M. B. Kabadi, K. B. Jabalpurwala and K. A. Venkatachalam, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1011.
7. R. A. Robinson and S. G. Stokes, 'Electrolytic solutions', 2nd edition, Butterworths, 1959, 468.
8. C. W. Davies, 'Ion Association', Butterworths, London, 1962, p. 41.